

SYSTEMATIC COMPARISON BETWEEN CARDING AND PAPER- MAKING METHOD FOR PRODUCING DISCONTINUOUS RECYCLED CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

The waste of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) accompanying with the increasing demand of carbon fiber (CF) has aroused the concern that the inadequate disposal of the relevant waste will ecologically and economically become a threat in future. Recycling the valuable CF in the wastes is a promising strategy but it is lack of good methods to apply the recycled carbon fibers (RCF), which are usually discontinuous and distribution-randomly shaped. In this paper, two kinds of manufacturing method for discontinuous RCF reinforced thermoplastics will be discussed in the details of relevant manufacturing characteristics and compared by the mechanical properties of the materials after compression molding. One is named as carbon fiber card web reinforced thermoplastics (CWT) and the other as carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT).

1 INTRODUCTION

High properties-weight efficiency of carbon fibers (CF) makes carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) a feasible solution for environment and resource concern [1-3]. A report predicted that the demand of CF would increase to 89,000 tons until 2020 [4]. The actual demand in 2013 is 46,500 tons and almost 75% higher than that in 2009, the economic recession year. Even compared with the year of 2008, the demand has increased by 48% [4]. The rapid increase of the CF demand will lead the surge of the relevant CFRP products in future. Aerospace and defence segment still possesses the largest application of total CFRP amount and it is also rewarded by the highest revenue rate. Based on the environment consideration and on the energy consumption efficiency of aeroplanes, CF are used in Boeing 787 for almost 50% of the airframe weight. In the segment of automotive, more and more CF is required to weight-lightening for the future automotive markets, which will be the mainstream in the

consideration of car designs. The BMW i-series just provided the evidence that weight-lightening strategies are met with the need of the future customers. In general speaking, an urgent change is happening in the transportation departments. The CFRP model of a car design will decrease the total weight by 30% and the cost of gasoline by 22.4% compared with traditional model, which mainly apply steel [5]. As a consequence of promoting the CF application, the environment issues such as the emission of carbon dioxide in atmosphere will be released. Additionally, CFRP is advanced material to support the innovation of engine systems driving a car with electronic power or other hybrid power. However, there are two kinds of CFRP wastes generated accordingly related to the increasing CFRP products. They are in-plant wastes and market wastes. The former account for 30% to 50% of the total wastes amount and they are generated during the manufacturing process [6]. On the contrary, the latter are generated after the CFRP products are retired. Based on the landfill capacity and environment concerns, recycling the CF of longer life than CFRP is the most attractive way to avoid additional burden and problems. There have been several researches about how to recycle the CF without sacrificing the mechanical properties [7-10]. In this work the recycling technology of depolymerisation under ordinary pressure is conducted to recycle the CF. Usually, the retired CFRP wastes are complicated by complex material structures and contaminated by other materials, such as glass fibers, metal and etc. Therefore, the relatively cleaner in-plant waste is the good RCF source for research and application. After developing the package methods of recycling CF from market wastes, the systematic application of RCF is expectable in the future. Furthermore, the potential capacity of RCF in future will be explored as a plausible supplying source. However, there are several problems should be discussed before the application consideration of RCF. The fiber length cannot be kept uniform after several processes during recycling and the fiber orientation distribution will be random.

In this paper, two kinds of manufacturing methods are discussed to use discontinuous RCF reinforced thermoplastics. One is carbon fiber card web reinforced thermoplastics (CWT) and the other is carbon fiber paper reinforced thermoplastics (CPT). CWT is made by a carding machine, which is composed of the needles of interactive perpendicular movements with a belt of unidirectional movement. The cooperative movements of the components of a carding machine make the resultant CWT containing the RCF re-aligned along the belt movement. The mechanical properties of CWT on different measuring directions will be investigated. Two kinds of volume fractions (V_f) will be investigated. Different from the carding process, paper-making process will introduce the water to improve the distribution of RCF. CPT will be compared with CWT to discuss the possible application of discontinuous RCF reinforced thermoplastics.

2 PREPARATION OF MATERIALS

2.1 Materials

Polyamide 6 (PA6) fibers from Mitsubishi Chemistry Co. are decided as the matrix. T300 fibers originally from Toray Industries Co. are recycled by means of depolymerisation technique of Hitachi Chemical Co., Ltd [11]. Recycled T300 fibers are called as R-T300 in following contents.

2.1 CWT preparation

Two V_f of RCF will be mixed with PA6 fibers, 20% and 40%. The CWT of different V_f are called as CWT20 and CWT40 respectively. The length of RCF, in this research, is 6mm. The fibers are fed into a carding machine without pre-operations. Figure 1 shows a schematic image of the carding process. The cooperatively perpendicular movements of needles with the moving belt together make a CWT sheet continuously. Without additional operations and agents, the carding process is economically efficient.

Figure 1: A schematic image of CWT preparation.

2.2 CPT preparation

The length of RCF and PA6 fiber were 6 mm. These fibers mixed together in container filled with water. A piece of CPT sheet will be prepared after stirring the mixture, as shown in Figure 2. Then the water will be dried for a few minutes. The size of prepared CPT sheet is limited by the container size.

Figure 2: A schematic image of CPT preparation.

2.3 Compression molding pressure

Compression molding is chosen as the manufacturing method since it is suitable to form complex shapes within a short cycle time. The mold size is 25 cm x 15 cm, so all the sheets of discontinuous RCF reinforced thermoplastics must be cut to fit the mold size. For CWT, 20 layers of CWT sheets will be put into the mold under the molding pressure of 7 MPa. For CPT, 18 layers of CPT sheets are used under the molding pressure of 5 MPa. In both formations, the molding temperature is 255 degrees Celsius. Before molding, the sheets will be dried over than 4 hours at 90 degrees Celsius.

2.4 Ash tests

Based on the concern of matrix resin will be squeezed out from the mold during compression molding. The actual V_f needs to be measured before investigating the mechanical properties. Ash tests are conducted. Three pieces of specimens were cut by the size of 10 mm x 15 mm x 3 mm. An oven (Elepot Co.) is used for burning off the resin and the temperature at 500 degrees Celsius. After 1 hour, the matrix resin will be totally burnt out, which will be checked by fiber surface observation. The density of R-T300 is 1.76 g/cm³ because the fibers were barely damaged by the recycling means of depolymerisation technique under ordinary pressure. The density of CWT specimens will be measured by an electronic densimeter (MDS 300, Alfa Mirage Co., Ltd). The weights of the specimens before and after burning are measured by an electronic balance (AUX320, Shimadzu Co., Ltd). Eqn (1) is used to calculate the actual V_f of CWT.

$$V_f = \frac{m_1 \rho_c}{m_0 \rho_f} \tag{1}$$

where m_0 is the weight of the specimen before ash test; m_1 is the weight of specimen after ash test by an electronic balance; ρ_f and ρ_c are the densities of the fiber and of the specimen respectively.

2.5 Digital microscope observation

In order to check whether the matrix resin is all burnt off in the oven, a digital microscope (VHX-1000, Keyence Co.) is used. Additionally, the impregnation status of CWT, whether there is lack of resin on the surface of the specimens in details, is observed.

2.6 Tensile tests

Tensile tests are conducted to investigate the effect of re-aligned RCF in CWT on the resultant mechanical properties. A universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AG-Xplus, Shimadzu Co.) is used in this research. The size of the specimens is 15 mm x 110 mm x 3 mm. 5 pieces of specimens are cut along longitudinal and transverse directions, which are called L-direction and T-direction respectively. The preparation process is illustrated in Figure 3. A strain sensor is applied during tensile tests and its gauge length is 25 mm. The installation is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: A schematic image of preparing the specimens of CWT for tensile tests.

Figure 4: The installation of strain sensor in tensile tests for CWT.

2.7 Three point bending tests

In the discussion of application of CWT and CPT, three point bending tests are conducted, which is believed an efficient to investigate the damage resistance of materials. A table-top type of universal testing machine (AUTOGRAPH AG-X, Shimadzu Co.). The span of the supporters on the testing machine is determined by the thickness of the specimens and the ratio of span to thickness is 16 to 1. Five pieces of specimens have been tested for each kind of materials, including CWT20, CWT40 and CPT.

2.8 Izod impact tests

The size of specimens is 10 mm x 50 mm x 3 mm and five pieces are investigated for each test. All the materials will be investigated. The Izod test machine is Instron Dynatup POE200e.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Digital microscope observation

The microscope images of the surfaces of CWT20 and CWT40 show that the higher content of RCF will hinder the resin flow during compression molding. In Figures 5 and 6, the white circles are the spots showing lack of resin.

Figure 5: A microscope image of CWT20 under magnification of 200x.

Figure 6: A microscope image of CWT40 under magnification of 200x.

3.2 Ash tests

The V_f are calculated by Eqn (1) and are listed in Table 1. They show that the actual V_f of CWT20 is around 25% and that of CWT40 is around 35%. Only the CPT contain the similar V_f with the expectation. The more resin of CWT flown out from the mold than that of CPT is attributed to the

higher compression molding pressure, which is 7 MPa for CWT and 5 MPa for CPT. Additionally, the actual V_f of CWT40 away from the expectation is probably because RCF hindered the resin flow. Furthermore, the rough manufacturing process of carding process made RCF drop off the machine.

Table 1: The results of ash tests

	Expected V_f	Actual* V_f
CWT20	20 %	26.8 %
CWT40	40 %	34.4 %
CPT	20 %	21.0 %

* Actual means the V_f calculated by Eqn. (1).

3.3 Tensile tests

Based on the characteristics of carding process, the RCF were concentrated along with the belt moving direction to some extends. The tensile modulus and strength of CWT show the anisotropic tendency when measuring on different directions, the L-direction and T-direction in this paper, as shown in Figures 7 and 8. After re-aligned, RCF in CWT will ease the difficulty of package and improve the potential V_f limit for the discontinuous RCF reinforced thermoplastics. However, in this paper, the actual V_f higher than expectation only happened in the case of CWT20, even the fiber orientation concentration is not the key factor. On the other hand, the aspect ratio (length to diameter) of the RCF is another factor determining the fiber orientation. The discontinuous RCF cannot ensure the constant aspect ratios and also may be damaged in the rough carding process, which is slightly presented by the ash tests results of CWT40.

Furthermore, both in tensile modulus and strength, the difference in percentage between the measuring directions of them are constant even the V_f has been increased. This illustrates that the RCF content is not the key factor affecting the fiber orientation distribution but mainly controlled by the carding process. Therefore, the carding process is highly potential to be improved with high controllability.

Figure 7: Tensile modulus of CWT.

Figure 8: Tensile strength of CWT.

3.4 Three point bending tests

In order to give the reference of the proper application of CWT and CPT, the results of three point bending tests are shown as Figure 9. The CWT20 has the higher flexural modulus when measuring along the L-direction. Based on the characteristics of CPT, the randomly orientated RCF contributed to CPT of higher flexural modulus than CWT20 when measuring in T-direction. Additionally, the actual V_f of CWT is higher than that of CPT, so the actual modulus is much higher in L-direction accompanying with the help of RCF alignment. On the contrary, the higher V_f will leave much more defects, such as fiber ends and larger parallel interfacial areas to the load. The defects will relatively easily lead the CWT20 weaker in T-direction, which cannot be compromised by higher RCF content. Even considering the actual V_f of CWT20 and CPT, the flexural modulus of L-direction of CWT20 is higher than CPT.

Figure 9: Flexural modulus of CPT and CWT20.

3.5 Izod impact tests

Accompanied with the results of tensile tests, the difference between the L-direction and the T-direction is almost constant even though the V_f is increased. However, the impact energy absorption decreased when the V_f increased, as shown in Figure 10. This is probably attributed to the increased fiber-fiber contact points and to the possible voids content.

On the contrary, the randomly distributed orientation of RCF improves the impact energy absorption. Figure 11 shows the impact energy absorption of CPT and CWT20. Even though CWT contains more RCF aligned along the L-direction, the impact energy absorption is not correspondingly enhanced. This is attributed to the fiber length of RCF and the other is the curve of RCF caused by the complex movements of a carding machine. Even though the actual V_f of CWT20 is more than that of CPT, the more and longer RCF in CPT contribute to the more promising impact energy absorption than CWT20.

Figure 10: Impact energy absorption results of Izod tests.

Figure 11: Impact energy absorption results of CPT and CWT20.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, carding process and paper-making process are introduced to produce discontinuous recycled carbon fibers reinforced thermoplastics. But the different characteristics of the two processes make the CWT and CPT of different characteristics.

From the mechanical properties of CWT:

- 1) The similar difference in percentage between the L- and T-direction illustrates that the fiber content will not largely affect the fiber re-alignment.
- 2) The increase of V_f caused the increase of tensile modulus but decrease of tensile strength. It is attributed to the increased weak points of CWT40 including more fiber-fiber contact points, more likely shortened RCF and more possible voids content.
- 3) Although a carding process is a cost efficient means for reusing RCF because of the fast continuous manufacturing without drying process, we have to be careful for quality assurance from above mentioned points.

From the comparison between CWT and CPT:

- 4) RCF is more uniformly dispersed in CPT than in CWT. In consequence, the minimum molding pressure of CPT is smaller than that of CWT, and mechanical properties of CPT are higher than those of CWT.
- 5) The high potential impact energy absorption of CPT illustrated that the fiber length and orientation distributions are the key factors of mechanical properties.

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